

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Danish consumers' knowledge about and willingness to buy dairy products close to the best-before-date

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Abstract

More than 700,000 tons of food are wasted annually in Denmark where dairy products are among the 10 most wasted food products. Therefore, this study aims to analyze Danish consumers' understanding of the best-before-date label and relational patterns for different knowledge-attitude-behavior factors influencing their willingness to buy (WTB) dairy products close to the best-before-date. Respondents ($n = 436$) from an online survey were segmented into four segments based on (i) their frequency of purchasing and (ii) their WTB dairy products close to the best-before-date: low/low ($n = 53$), medium/low ($n = 149$), medium/high ($n = 190$), and high/high ($n = 44$). All four segments had a relatively high understanding of the best-before-date label (total mean score = 2.43). For the medium/high and high/high segments, drivers for buying dairy products close to the best-before-date were avoidance of food waste, reduced price, and organic certification. However, the low/low and medium/low segments refrained from purchasing dairy products close to the best-before-date due to health concerns and low-quality perception and found them unappetizing. Furthermore, there seems to be a tendency for an age-dependent pattern. Older respondents (low/low and medium/low) had a higher risk perception than the younger respondents (medium/high and high/high). Consumers' level of risk perception and food disgust sensitivity are the actual drivers or barriers for consumers' WTB dairy products close to the best-before-date and not their level of knowledge. The results obtained from this study contribute valuable insights into consumer values and can be crucial for developing strategies to reduce food waste in an environment where consumers make their purchasing decisions.

KEYWORDS

best-before-date, consumer behavior, consumer knowledge, dairy products, food waste, willingness to buy

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1 | INTRODUCTION

According to the Danish Agriculture and Food Council (DAFC) (2015), over 700,000 tons of edible food are wasted in Denmark annually. Danish households are responsible for most of this food waste (~260,000 tons annually), while retailers account for the second largest part, with 163,000 tons annually (DAFC, 2015; Halloran et al., 2014). The predominating food waste at these later stages of the food supply chain has a higher environmental impact than food waste at earlier stages due to the accumulation of used resources and CO₂ emissions (Jensen & Teuber, 2018; Priefer et al., 2016). For food waste to be minimized at the retail and household level, it is necessary to understand which factors influence consumer behavior in these later stages of the food supply chain.

European Union (EU) legislation states that two types of date labels, best-before and use-by, may be used on food products. The first refers to food quality, while the latter refers to food quality and safety (European Union, 2011). Date labels are communication tools to help guide consumers about the quality and safety of food products (Hansen & Lähteenmäki, 2021). Confusion regarding the meaning of the different date labels may cause consumers to waste food unnecessarily because they throw out edible products labeled with a best-before-date.

Several studies have been conducted to identify the causes of food waste at the Danish household level (Beck et al., 2011; Gjerris & Gaiani, 2013; Halloran et al., 2014; Hansen & Lähteenmäki, 2020, 2021; Laasholdt et al., 2021; Stancu & Lähteenmäki, 2018). Some of the causes identified were a hectic lifestyle, increased availability of affordable food, impulsive shopping behavior, and lack of planning (Gjerris & Gaiani, 2013; Laasholdt et al., 2021; Stancu & Lähteenmäki, 2018). Lastly, confusion regarding date labeling and uncertainty about shelf life after opening a food product seems to play an important role (Beck et al., 2011; Halloran et al., 2014; Stancu & Lähteenmäki, 2018).

In a recent study by Hansen and Lähteenmäki (2020), Danish consumers' knowledge about the meaning of the best-before label was investigated. It was found that 84% of respondents were aware of the meaning of the date label. However, Danish consumers' relatively high knowledge of the best-before-date label is not to the same extent translated into the desired behavior to avoid food waste. Hansen and Lähteenmäki (2021) also found that consumers' risk perception associated with eating food after it had passed the best-before-date had a significant impact on their intention to throw out a product. Moreover, there also seems to be a relationship between food waste, best-before-date labeling, and product type. Perishable foods such as meat and some types of dairy products are thrown away in larger quantities compared to other product types (Halloran et al., 2014; Laasholdt et al., 2021; Stancu & Lähteenmäki, 2018). It is estimated that ~7%-10% of all dairy products are wasted at consumption levels in the European Union (Gustavsson et al., 2011; Herzberg et al., 2020). According to the Danish Agriculture and Food Council (DAFC, 2015), dairy products are among the 10 most wasted food products in Denmark. This is problematic since the carbon footprint of many types of dairy products (e.g., cheese and butter) is relatively high (Gaillac & Marbach, 2021; Kumar & Choubey, 2022; Sahu & Agarwal, 2021).

In Thompson et al. (2018), participants' willingness to consume (WTC) dairy products concerning the best-before-date was investigated. It was found that different levels of risk perception would influence the participants' WTC. However, the relationship between consumers' perception of dairy products close to the best-before-date and their willingness to buy (WTB) these products is not well understood. Hence, to minimize the unnecessary waste of dairy products, there is a need for a better understanding of the factors that influence consumers' perception of dairy products close to the best-before-date. The fact that consumers seem confused about date labeling is an interesting observation that will be subjected to further analysis in this study. Lastly, this study presents a survey designed according to the Knowledge-Attitude-Behavior (KAB) theory (Andrade et al., 2020). By including the three KAB factors, this study aims to analyze Danish consumers' understanding of the best-before-date label concerning dairy products and analyze relational patterns in KAB factors influencing their WTB dairy products close to the best-before-date.

2 | METHOD

2.1 | Survey design and data collection

Data were collected using a questionnaire created in SurveyXact. The questionnaire was formulated in English and then translated into Danish, making the questionnaire available for both Danish- and English-speaking respondents. The Danish-speaking authors conducted both the formulation and translation. The questionnaire was pre-tested by five Danish- and English-speaking individuals before final data collection. Pre-testing was performed to ensure that the questionnaire was understandable and consistent and that the positioning of the questions and the sections was in order. The recruitment of participants took place through Facebook by snowball sampling (Abubakar et al., 2015). The link to the questionnaire was shared through the authors' Facebook networks as well as the groups "Frederiksberg Campus," "FEF KU-science," and "Questionnaire group/survey group" between the 17th and 24th of May 2022. A total of 517 respondents replied to the survey; 436 of them completed all questions included in the survey.

The study followed the Declaration of Helsinki, and the procedures were approved by the Research Ethics Committee of Science and Health, University of Copenhagen (ReF: 504-0362/22-5000). Participants were asked to consent to the use of their data in the present study according to the General Data Protecting Regulation. Furthermore, they were informed that all responses would be anonymous and that they had the opportunity to withdraw their consent at any time. Questions regarding socio-demographic characteristics were collected in the first part of the survey. In the second part, the participants were asked about their understanding of the best-before-date label. The participants were provided three statements of which two were correct and one was incorrect. The statements are listed in Table 1. The statements were modified from Thompson et al. (2018) to fit the aim of this study. Furthermore, to ensure the measurement of the

TABLE 1 Selected questions and corresponding answers from the questionnaire.

Topic	KAB factors	Items	Response options
Understanding of the best-before-date label	Knowledge ^a	The best-before-date label means that the food can be consumed after this date, but it may no longer be of its best quality. (Correct)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Correct • Incorrect • Don't know The response options are for all three statements.
		The best-before-date label means that the product will be safe to eat until this date but should not be eaten past this date. (Incorrect)	
		The best-before-date label means that the product still can be eaten even though the date has expired. (Correct)	
Willingness to buy products close to best-before-date	Behavior ^{a,b}	Which of the following dairy product categories do you buy close to the best-before-date?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Milk and cream • Fermented dairy products (e.g., sour cream, yoghurt, A38, and buttermilk) • Cheese • Butter • Milk beverages (e.g., cacao milk, iced coffee, and drinkable yogurt) • I do not buy dairy products close to the best-before-date • Never • Rarely • Once in a while • Often • Always • On the best-before-date shown • One day before the best-before-date • Two days before the best-before-date • Three days before the best-before-date • Four days before the best-before-date • Five days before the best-before-date • Do not care about the best-before-date • Don't know
		How often do you buy dairy products close to the best-before-date? (Frequency concerning segmentation)	
		Indicate when you would buy a dairy product relative to the best-before-date on the product. (WTB concerning segmentation)	

(Continues)

TABLE 1 (Continued)

Topic	KAB factors	Items	Response options
Possible factors influencing willingness to buy	Attitude ^c	<p>Indicate how much you agree with the following statements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> I buy dairy products close to the best-before-date because of environmental concerns. I buy dairy products close to the best-before-date because of the reduced price. I buy dairy products close to the best-before-date because it is a common thing to do in my network. I buy dairy products close to the best-before-date if they are organic. I buy dairy products close to the best-before-date if they are conventionally produced. I buy dairy products close to the best-before-date to avoid food waste. I buy dairy products close to the best-before-date because it is easily accessible. I buy dairy products close to the best-before-date if it comes from a specific brand. I do not buy dairy products close to the best-before-date because I find it unappetizing. I do not buy dairy products close to the best-before-date because of health concerns. I do not buy dairy products close to the best-before-date because they will no longer be of their best quality. 	<p>Evaluate on a five-point Likert scale for all the attitudes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Totally disagree Disagree Neither agree nor disagree Agree Totally agree <p>The response options are for all of the statements.</p>

Abbreviations: KAB, Knowledge–Attitude–Behavior; WTB, willingness to buy.

^aThompson et al. (2018).

^bDAFAC (2022).

^cMeigaard et al. (2016).

FIGURE 1 The four segments are based on dairy purchase frequency close to the best-before-date and willingness to buy dairy products close to the best-before-date. Yellow = Low/Low segment, Red = Medium/Low segment, Blue = Medium/High segment, and Green = High/High segment. Values on the x-axis: 1 = “Never,” 2 = “Rarely,” 3 = “Once in a while,” 4 = “Often,” 5 = “Always.” Values on the y-axis: 1 = “Don’t know,” 2 = “Do not care about the best-before-date,” 3 = “5 days before the best-before-date,” 4 = “4 days before the best-before-date,” 5 = “3 days before the best-before-date,” 6 = “2 days before the best-before-date,” 7 = “1 day before the best-before-date,” 8 = “On the best-before-date shown.”

participant’s knowledge about the best-before-date label, a definition of the best-before-date label was not given beforehand.

The questionnaire included questions about the participants’ purchase frequency of dairy products close to the best-before-date and their WTB of different types of dairy products close to the best-before-date. The different dairy product types were chosen based on inspiration from Thompson et al. (2018) and the general Danish classification of dairy products (DAFC, 2022).

A five-point Likert scale ranging from “totally disagree” to “totally agree” was used to measure 11 attitudinal statements regarding the participants’ WTB dairy products close to the best-before-date. The Likert scale was used since it is a verified measurement method (Meilgaard et al., 2016). The 11 statements are provided in Table 1. All of the statements were self-developed by the authors and designed for this specific study.

Table 1 gives an overview of the question formulation and possible response options concerning the participant’s knowledge of the best-

before-date label, their WTB dairy products close to the best-before-date, and possible factors influencing their WTB these products.

2.2 | Data preprocessing and analysis

The collected data were extracted from SurveyXact and transferred to Excel (Version 2202; Microsoft Office 365) for further analysis. Participants answering “No” to the question “Do you buy dairy products?” were excluded ($n = 11$). All incomplete responses ($n = 70$) were removed from the dataset resulting in 436 useful responses. Regarding the question “Who is responsible for the grocery shopping in your household?”, the answer option “Other” had several different replies. Those who answered, “Only me” and “We shop individually” were assigned the category “Primarily me.” For the ones answering “My parents,” a new category called “Parents” was created.

For the three statements examining the participants' knowledge of the best-before-date label (Table 1), a combined knowledge score was calculated for each respondent. One point was given for a correct answer, while zero points were given for an incorrect or "I don't know" answer. This resulted in a knowledge score ranging from 0 to 3. A knowledge score of 0 indicated no understanding of the best-before-date label statements, whereas a knowledge score of 3 indicated a complete understanding of the best-before-date label statements (Pandey et al., 2021; Pieniak et al., 2010). Moreover, the responses from the attitudinal statements were recoded to numbers ranging from 1 to 5, where 1 was "Totally disagree" and 5 was "Totally agree." In addition, the responses to the question concerning the frequency of buying dairy products close to the best-before-date were recoded to numbers ranging from 1 to 5, where 1 was "Never" and 5 was "Always." The responses to the question regarding the participants' WTB dairy products close to the best-before-date were likewise recoded to numbers from 1 to 8.

The statistical analysis was performed in RStudio (Version 4.2.0). All the categorical variables were quantified by percentages and counts, whereas the continuous variables were quantified as means and standard deviations. The respondents were segmented based on (i) how frequently they would buy dairy products close to the best-before-date and (ii) their WTB dairy products close to the best-before-date. The segmentation was done manually by plotting the two abovementioned variables against each other.

This resulted in four segments: Low Frequency/Low Willingness (Low/Low), Medium Frequency/Low Willingness (Medium/Low), Medium Frequency/High Willingness (Medium/High), and High Frequency/High Willingness (High/High). Participants having a dairy purchase frequency of 1 ("Never") were assigned to the Low/Low segment (x-axis in Figure 1). Participants with a dairy purchase frequency of 2 ("Rarely") or 3 ("Once in a while") were first assigned to one large group and then further divided into two groups based on their WTB dairy products close to the best-before-date (y-axis in Figure 1). The participants with a WTB ranging from 1 to 4 were assigned to the Medium/Low segment, while participants with a WTB ranging from 5 to 8 were assigned to the Medium/High segment. Lastly, all participants having a dairy purchase frequency of 4 ("Often") or 5 ("Always") were assigned to the High/High segment. The plot used for the segmentation is illustrated in Figure 1.

Logistic regression was used to investigate the probability of belonging to the different segments based on certain socio-demographic variables (gender, age, and education) as well as attitudinal statements. An odds ratio (OR) and a confidence interval (CI) were calculated for each attitudinal statement for each segment. The dependent variables were the memberships to the specific segment, while the continuous independent variables were the various attitudinal statements regarding the participants' WTB dairy products close to the best-before-date. Therefore, an $OR > 1$ indicates a higher probability of belonging to a specific segment, while an $OR < 1$ indicates a lower probability of belonging to a specific segment. Furthermore, an $OR = 1$ indicates that the statement does not affect

the belongingness to a specific statement (Szumilas, 2010). The logistic regression models were adjusted for age.

The data distribution concerning the attitudinal statements was checked for normality by a Shapiro test. Due to data being non-parametric, a Wilcoxon rank sum test was used to analyze possible pairwise significant differences between the four segments. Significant differences between the segments were indicated by different superscript lowercase letters, where the highest mean was assigned to the letter a. In the data analysis, only results with a p -value of .05 or below were considered statistically significant.

3 | RESULTS

The distribution of the socio-demographic characteristics between the different segments is presented in Table 2. The majority of the 436 respondents were female (72.7%). The average age of the respondents was 40 years (ranging from 18 to 96 years). Age was significantly related to WTB dairy products close to the best-before-date, where an average age below 39 years was associated with higher WTB. Almost two-thirds (65.2%) of the respondents had a medium-high education or higher. More than half (54.1%) of the respondents were living in the Capital Region of Denmark, whereas the rest were mainly living in the Central Denmark Region (20.4%) and Region Zealand (16.7%). Furthermore, more than 90% of the respondents participated in grocery shopping. In general, the higher educational level seems weakly associated with a higher frequency of dairy purchases, while there was no remarkable relation between segments and gender. Due to the unequal gender distribution and the significant differences between the segments' mean age and educational level, adjustments for these independent variables were conducted in the logistic regression models to minimize the effect of selection bias (Ranganathan et al., 2017).

Table 3 shows the mean knowledge score for the different segments and the total sample regarding the understanding of the best-before-date label. The total mean score was 2.43, which corresponds to a relatively high understanding since a score of 3 corresponds to complete knowledge. No significant difference between the segments was found.

Figure 2 shows that the majority of Low/Low (92.5%) and Medium/Low (65.8%) segments, did not buy dairy products close to the best-before-date. The primary dairy products bought by the Medium/High and High/High segments were "Fermented dairy products," "Cheese," and "Milk and cream." For all segments, "Butter" and "Milk beverages" such as cacao milk and iced coffee were the least frequently purchased dairy categories.

3.1 | Segmentation concerning attitudes

Table 4 shows the mean values and standard deviations for the degree of agreement with the different attitudinal statements for the four

TABLE 2 Socio-demographic characteristics of the four segments and the total sample.

Variables ^a	Low/Low (n = 53)	Medium/ Low (n = 149)	Medium/ High (n = 190)	High/High (n = 44)	p-value	Total sample (n = 436)	Percentage
Gender (%(n))					.121		
Female	54.7 (29)	73.8 (110)	75.3 (143)	79.5 (35)		317	72.7
Male	45.3 (24)	25.5 (38)	24.2 (46)	20.5 (9)		117	26.8
Other	0.0 (0)	0.0 (0)	0.5 (1)	0.0 (0)		1	0.2
Do not wish to answer	0.0 (0)	0.7 (1)	0.0 (0)	0.0 (0)		1	0.2
Age (mean ± SD)	46.3 ± 13.3	41.8 ± 15.4	38.9 ± 13.0	35.0 ± 11.0	<.001	40.4 ± 14.0	
Education (%(n))					.008		
Primary education	0.0 (0)	0.7 (1)	2.1 (4)	0.0 (0)		5	1.1
Upper secondary education	5.7 (3)	16.8 (25)	12.1 (23)	11.4 (5)		56	12.8
Apprenticeship	9.4 (5)	10.7 (16)	6.8 (13)	13.6 (6)		40	9.2
Short higher education (2 years)	15.1 (8)	10.7 (16)	13.7 (26)	0.0 (0)		50	11.5
Medium higher education (3–4 years)	60.4 (32)	41.6 (62)	34.7 (66)	52.3 (23)		183	42.0
Long higher education (5 years or more)	9.4 (5)	18.8 (28)	30.5 (58)	22.7 (10)		101	23.2
Do not wish to answer	0.0 (0)	0.7 (1)	0.0 (0)	0.0 (0)		1	0.2
Income (%(n))					.273		
Less than 150.000	5.7 (3)	19.5 (29)	15.8 (30)	20.5 (9)		71	16.3
150.000–299.999	11.3 (6)	11.4 (17)	9.5 (18)	22.7 (10)		51	11.7
300.000–449.999	20.8 (11)	15.4 (23)	20.0 (38)	20.5 (9)		81	18.6
450.000–599.999	18.9 (10)	15.4 (23)	22.1 (42)	13.6 (6)		81	18.6
600.000–749.999	17.0 (9)	8.7 (13)	8.9 (17)	6.8 (3)		42	9.6
750.000–899.999	9.4 (5)	10.1 (15)	7.9 (15)	9.1 (4)		39	8.9
900.000 or above	9.4 (5)	12.8 (19)	10.5 (20)	0.0 (0)		44	10.1
Do not wish to answer	7.5 (4)	6.7 (10)	5.3 (10)	6.8 (3)		27	6.2
Region (%(n))					.208		
Capital Region of Denmark	62.3 (33)	57.7 (86)	48.9 (93)	54.5 (24)		236	54.1
Region Zealand	13.2 (7)	18.8 (28)	14.7 (28)	22.7 (10)		73	16.7
Central Region Denmark	13.2 (7)	15.4 (23)	25.8 (49)	22.7 (10)		89	20.4
Region of Southern Denmark	5.7 (3)	5.4 (8)	6.3 (12)	0.0 (0)		23	5.3
North Denmark Region	5.7 (3)	2.7 (4)	4.2 (8)	0.0 (0)		15	3.4
Household (%(n))					.779		
Alone	17.0 (9)	20.1 (30)	14.2 (27)	18.2 (8)		74	17.0
With spouse/partner	26.4 (14)	31.5 (47)	32.1 (61)	29.5 (13)		135	31.0
With spouse/partner and children	47.2 (25)	30.2 (45)	38.9 (74)	29.5 (13)		157	36.0
Single parent	7.5 (4)	8.7 (13)	5.8 (11)	11.4 (5)		33	7.6
With parent(s)	0.0 (0)	2.7 (4)	1.6 (3)	2.3 (1)		8	1.8
With roommate(s)	1.9 (1)	6.0 (9)	5.8 (11)	6.8 (3)		24	5.5
Other	0.0 (0)	0.7 (1)	1.6 (3)	2.3 (1)		5	1.1
Shopping responsible (%(n))					.204		
Parents	0.0 (0)	1.3 (2)	0.5 (1)	0.0 (0)		3	0.7
Primarily me	52.8 (28)	55.0 (82)	52.1 (99)	65.9 (29)		238	54.6

(Continues)

TABLE 2 (Continued)

Variables ^a	Low/Low (n = 53)	Medium/ Low (n = 149)	Medium/ High (n = 190)	High/High (n = 44)	p-value	Total sample (n = 436)	Percentage
My partner	15.1 (8)	8.1 (12)	7.9 (15)	2.3 (1)		36	8.3
We share responsibility	32.1 (17)	35.6 (53)	39.5 (75)	31.8 (14)		159	36.5

Continuous variables are presented as means \pm standard deviations (SD). Significant results ($p \leq .05$) are marked in bold. Low/Low = Low frequency of purchased dairy products close to the best-before-date/low willingness to buy (WTB) dairy products close to the best-before-date. Medium/Low = Medium frequency of purchased dairy products close to the best-before-date/low WTB dairy products close to the best-before-date. Medium/High = Medium frequency of purchased dairy products close to the best-before-date/high WTB dairy products close to the best-before-date. High/High = High frequency of purchased dairy products close to the best-before-date/high WTB dairy products close to the best-before-date.

^aCategorical variables are presented as percentages (%) and counts (n).

TABLE 3 Knowledge score regarding the understanding of the best-before-date label distributed by segments.

Knowledge score ^a	Low/Low (n = 53)	Medium/Low (n = 149)	Medium/High (n = 190)	High/High (n = 44)	Total sample (n = 436)	p-value
mean \pm SD	2.40 \pm 0.79	2.31 \pm 0.86	2.49 \pm 0.72	2.57 \pm 0.66	2.43 \pm 0.78	.092

Abbreviations: n, counts; SD, standard deviation.

^aThe knowledge score was based on the following three statements: "The best-before-date label means that the food can be consumed after this date, but it may no longer be of its best quality" (correct). "The best-before-date label means that the product will be safe to eat until this date but should not be eaten past this date" (incorrect). "The best-before-date label means that the product still can be eaten even though the date has expired" (correct). One point was given for a correct answer, while 0 points were given for an incorrect or "I don't know" answer. A score of 3 was the highest achievable score and was regarded as complete knowledge. The significant level was set at $\leq .05$.

TABLE 4 Degree of agreement for the different attitudinal statements for the four different segments.

	Low/Low	Medium/Low	Medium/High	High/High
Environmental concerns	2.02 \pm 1.01d	2.63 \pm 1.14c	2.94 \pm 1.19b	3.50 \pm 1.07a
Reduced price	2.74 \pm 1.39c	3.20 \pm 1.16b	3.89 \pm 1.05a	4.18 \pm 1.0a
Social common	1.60 \pm 0.84a	1.87 \pm 0.88a	1.98 \pm 0.98a	2.00 \pm 0.86a
Organic	1.75 \pm 0.94d	2.40 \pm 1.05c	2.84 \pm 1.18b	3.34 \pm 1.24a
Conventional	1.89 \pm 0.97d	2.30 \pm 0.93c	2.52 \pm 1.04b	2.93 \pm 1.15a
Health concerns	2.70 \pm 1.10a	2.43 \pm 1.05a	1.72 \pm 0.81b	1.32 \pm 0.67c
Unappetizing	3.36 \pm 1.40a	2.73 \pm 1.15b	1.90 \pm 0.95c	1.34 \pm 0.75d
Lack of quality	3.40 \pm 1.18a	2.87 \pm 1.06b	2.04 \pm 0.97c	1.82 \pm 1.04c
Avoid food waste	2.36 \pm 1.26d	3.28 \pm 1.23c	3.63 \pm 1.20b	4.07 \pm 0.87a
Easily accessible	1.77 \pm 0.91c	2.49 \pm 0.98b	2.82 \pm 0.97a	2.89 \pm 0.84a
Specific brand	1.83 \pm 0.98b	2.31 \pm 1.05a	2.29 \pm 1.04a	2.25 \pm 1.10ab

segments. Significant differences between the four segments were found for all attitudes except for the social common attitude

Attitudinal statement values from the five-point Likert scale were recoded to numbers ranging from 1 to 5, where 1 was "Totally disagree" and 5 was "Totally agree." Values are expressed as means \pm SD. Significant differences between the segments are indicated by different superscript lowercase letters, where the highest mean is assigned to the letter a. The significant level was set at $\leq .05$. Low/Low = Low frequency of purchased dairy products close to the best-before-date/low WTB dairy products close to the best-before-date. Medium/Low = Medium frequency of purchased dairy products close to the best-before-date/low WTB dairy products close to the

best-before-date. Medium/High = Medium frequency of purchased dairy products close to the best-before-date/high WTB dairy products close to the best-before-date. High/High = High frequency of purchased dairy products close to the best-before-date/high WTB dairy products close to the best-before-date.

Table 5 shows the likelihood of belonging to the different segments according to the different attitudes. The respondents belonging to the Low/Low and Medium/Low segments were characterized by not buying dairy products close to the best-before-date due to health concerns, lack of quality, and because they found the products unappetizing. On the other hand, the Medium/High segment was characterized by an increased WTB when the dairy products were at a reduced

FIGURE 2 Preferred dairy product category to buy close to the best-before-date divided by segments. Results are expressed as a percentage of respondents. Low/Low = Low frequency of purchased dairy products close to the best-before-date/low willingness to buy (WTB) dairy products close to the best-before-date. Medium/Low = Medium frequency of purchased dairy products close to the best-before-date/low WTB dairy products close to the best-before-date. Medium/High = Medium frequency of purchased dairy products close to the best-before-date/high WTB dairy products close to the best-before-date. High/High = High frequency of purchased dairy products close to the best-before-date/high WTB dairy products close to the best-before-date.

TABLE 5 Likelihood of belonging to the segments by the attitudes.

Total (n = 436)	Low/Low (n = 53)	Medium/Low (n = 149)	Medium/High (n = 190)	High/High (n = 44)
I buy dairy products close to the Best-before-date ...	OR (CI)	OR (CI)	OR (CI)	OR (CI)
To avoid food waste	0.53 (0.42–0.68)***	0.91 (0.78–1.08)	1.24 (1.06–1.47)**	1.76 (1.27–2.56)**
If they are conventionally produced	0.58 (0.42–0.79)***	0.86 (0.71–1.05)	1.16 (0.96–1.35)	1.72 (1.25–2.18)**
Because it is easily accessible	0.38 (0.26–0.53)***	0.90 (0.73–1.10)	1.46 (1.19–1.81)***	1.37 (0.99–1.92)
Because of environmental concerns	0.55 (0.41–0.72)***	0.87 (0.73–1.04)	1.16 (0.98–1.38)	1.80 (1.34–2.21)***
If they are organic	0.47 (0.33–0.63)***	0.79 (0.66–0.94)**	1.31 (1.11–1.56)**	1.82 (2.14–2.20)***
Because of the reduced price.	0.61 (0.48–0.78)***	0.71 (0.59–0.84)***	1.57 (1.30–1.90)***	1.79 (1.26–2.69)**
Because it is a common thing to do in my network	0.62 (0.42–0.88)**	0.95 (0.76–1.18)	1.18 (0.96–1.46)	1.17 (0.92–1.63)
If it comes from a specific brand	0.65 (0.46–0.88)**	1.11 (0.92–1.35)	1.05 (0.87–1.27)	1.02 (0.74–1.26)
Because I find it unappetizing	2.12 (1.65–2.78)***	1.59 (1.34–1.89)***	0.57 (0.47–0.69)***	0.29 (0.16–0.46)***
Because of health concerns	1.95 (1.47–2.63)***	1.77 (1.44–2.19)***	0.53 (0.42–0.66)***	0.31 (0.21–0.51)***
Because they will no longer be of their best quality	2.26 (1.70–3.08)***	1.64 (1.36–1.97)***	0.53 (0.43–0.64)***	0.52 (0.36–0.73)***

Note: Odds ratio (OR) > 1 indicates a higher probability of belonging to a specific segment, while OR < 1 indicates a lower probability of belonging to a specific segment. OR = 1 indicates that the statement does not affect the belongingness to a specific statement. A confidence interval (CI), which does not include 1, indicates that 95% of the respondents will be more or less likely to belong to the specific segment. All significant results are marked in bold, and the following ranking system for the significance level was used: * $p = .05$, ** $p = .01$, *** $p \leq .001$. $n =$ counts.

price and easily accessible. Moreover, avoiding food waste was also an important factor for this segment. Important characteristics for the High/High segment were avoidance of food waste, environmental concerns, and if products were organic. Contrary to the Low/Low and Medium/Low segments, the Medium/High and High/High segments' WTB dairy products close to the best-before-date were not affected by health concerns. Furthermore, the Medium/High and High/High segments did not find dairy products close to the best-before-date to be unappetizing or lacking quality.

4 | DISCUSSION

This study investigated Danish consumers' knowledge about the best-before-date label and relational patterns in KAB factors influencing their WTB dairy products close to the best-before-date.

Knowledge: It was found that all four segments had a relatively high understanding of the best-before-date labels' meaning, with no significant difference between them (Table 3). These results are consistent with the findings of Hansen and Lähteenmäki (2020), where 84% of Danish consumers were found to be aware of the meaning of the best-before-date label (Hansen & Lähteenmäki, 2020). Within this relatively homogeneous study group regarding the knowledge of the meaning of the best-before-date, four consumer segments were identified based on purchase frequency and WTB dairy products close to the best-before-date.

Attitude: Consumers belonging to the Low/Low or Medium/Low segments were significantly more likely to state that they did not buy dairy products close to the best-before-date due to health concerns and low-quality perception (Tables 4 and 5). This is comparable to the findings of Thompson et al. (2018), where respondents who reported higher risk perceptions were more likely to report lower WTC dairy products close to the best-before-date. In Thompson et al. (2018), risk perception was, among other things, linked to food safety and food quality, which are comparable to the attitudes about health concerns and low-quality perception in this study. The fact that risk perception has an impact on consumers' WTB and WTC foods close to the best-before-date has also been shown in relation to other food groups, such as meat, fish, and vegetables (Hansen & Lähteenmäki, 2021; Loebnitz & Grunert, 2018; Tsiros & Heilman, 2005).

The Low/Low and Medium/Low segments were also significantly more likely to state that they did not buy dairy products close to the best-before-date because they find these products to be unappetizing. How consumers judge the edibility of foods has previously been related to feelings of disgust (Blichfeldt et al., 2015). Consumers' susceptibility to becoming disgusted by certain food cues can be referred to as food disgust sensitivity (Hartmann & Siegrist, 2018). In addition, consumers with a high food disgust sensitivity will be more easily influenced by food cues that indicate decay, such as the best-before-date (Stancu & Lähteenmäki, 2022). In general, consumers with a high food disgust sensitivity are more likely to waste food (Egolf et al., 2018). In Stancu and Lähteenmäki (2022), food disgust sensitivity was positively correlated with discarding food products past the best-before-date.

However, these studies (Egolf et al., 2018; Stancu & Lähteenmäki, 2022) refer to food waste on a household level, whereas this study focuses on the prevention of food waste at the retail level through consumers WTB dairy products close to the best-before-date. Although food waste was not directly investigated in this study, the results indicate that the Low/Low and Low/Medium segments are generally less willing to buy products close to the best-before-date and hence do not contribute to food waste prevention at the retail level due to their higher risk perception and food disgust sensitivity.

The mean ages of the Low/Low and Medium/Low segments (46 and 42 years, respectively) were higher compared to the Medium/High and High/High segments (39 and 35 years, respectively). These findings indicate a negative relationship between increasing age and WTB dairy products close to the best-before-date, which could be explained by the segments' higher risk perception and food disgust sensitivity. In a study by Egolf et al. (2018), age was also found to be positively associated with higher food disgust sensitivity. The higher food disgust sensitivity for the higher-aged respondents may be explained by several underlying factors, such as increased perception of vulnerability to disease or previous negative experiences with certain types of products (Egolf et al., 2018; Sanlier, 2009; Toma et al., 2020).

Consumers belonging to the Medium/High or High/High segments were significantly more likely to state that they would buy dairy products close to the best-before-date due to reduced price, environmental concern, avoidance of food waste, and if the products were organic (Tables 4 and 5). The finding that pricing seems to be an important driver for these two segments is not surprising. Studies have shown that reduced pricing may positively impact consumers' WTB if they are familiar with such pricing strategy (Aschemann-Witzel, 2018; Theotokis et al., 2012). However, for other consumers, like the ones belonging to the Low/Low and Medium/Low segments, reduced pricing may impact them negatively since this pricing strategy can amplify their risk perception or food disgust sensitivity (Theotokis et al., 2012). For example, concerning food disgust sensitivity, reduced price labels may act as food cues that increase the consumers' perception of decay (Egolf et al., 2018; Stancu & Lähteenmäki, 2022).

Even though the Medium/High and High/High segments were similar in many ways, the High/High segment differed significantly from the Medium/High segment by being more environmentally conscious. In Stancu and Lähteenmäki (2022), the relationship between consumer self-identities and food waste at the household level was examined. It was found that pro-environmental self-identities were negatively associated with discarding food past the best-before-date (Stancu & Lähteenmäki, 2022). Therefore, consumers who see themselves as environmentally friendly may be more willing to reduce food waste at the household level but also at the retail level by purchasing food close to the best-before-date.

Furthermore, it was found that the High/High segments were significantly more likely to state that they would buy dairy products close to the best-before-date if they were organically produced. This is an interesting observation since consumers often perceive organic foods as more nutritious, natural, and environmentally friendly compared to conventional alternatives (Gundala & Singh, 2021). However, the

literature indicates that consumers are not consistent in their interpretation of what is organic.

Furthermore, both drivers and barriers to purchasing organic foods seem to differ greatly among consumers (Buder et al., 2014; Hughner et al., 2007; Rana & Paul, 2020; Yiridoe et al., 2005). Several studies have shown that price is one of the main barriers to not purchasing organic products, especially for price-sensitive consumers (Buder et al., 2014; Hughner et al., 2007; Yiridoe et al., 2005). Considering this, it could indicate that the product type (organic or conventional) is subordinate to the High/High segment and that reduced price is the main driver behind these results. Furthermore, the High/High segment may not differentiate between avoiding food waste and being environmentally conscious, which makes them willing to buy all types of dairy products close to the best-before-date. For the younger age group of respondents, which dominated the Medium/High and High/High segments, a further explanation may be a higher awareness level and sustainability knowledge. As such, the age-dependent enabling or inhibiting drivers toward WTB close to best-before-date products may be due to differences in knowledge and awareness, which may be mitigated by nudging instruments (Pandey, Budhathoki, Feng, et al., 2023; Pandey, Budhathoki, Perez-Cueto, et al., 2023; Pandey, Olsen, et al., 2023).

Behavior: Despite the high level of knowledge regarding the meaning of the best-before-label, consumers from the Low/Low and Medium/Low segments were less willing to buy dairy products close to the best-before-date compared to the Medium/High and High/High segments. Similar to the finding of this study, Thompson et al. (2018) found no direct association between knowledge of the best-before-date label and WTC, meaning that the participants' WTC was not affected by their level of knowledge (Thompson et al., 2018). This suggests that consumers' level of risk perception and food disgust sensitivity are the actual drivers or barriers for consumers' WTB dairy products close to the best-before-date and not their level of knowledge concerning the best-before-date label.

The four segments' preferences for buying different dairy product categories close to the best-before-date were examined (Figure 2). It was found that the product categories with the shortest shelf life, "Fermented dairy products" and "Milk and cream," disregarding "Cheese," were the most frequently bought, close to the best-before-date. This tendency was the strongest for the Medium/High and High/High segments. On the other hand, product categories with a longer shelf life, such as "Butter" and "Milk beverages," were purchased less frequently. This could indicate that dairy products with shorter shelf life are often more accessible and close to the best-before-date. This would make sense since products with a short shelf life (e.g., milk) usually have a faster turnover rate compared to products with a longer shelf life (e.g., butter), which could result in increased frequency of the option to occur. However, this does not explain the results observed with cheese close to the best-before-date. In Thompson et al. (2018), consumers' WTC was investigated in relation to different types of dairy products and the best-before-date. Here, no significant difference in WTC was observed between cheese and yoghurt close to the best-before-date, which is similar to the findings of this study. However, the results by

Thompson et al. (2018) indicated that product type is considered when consumers choose a product close to the best-before-date. It was suggested that the consumer decision about buying a product close to the best-before-date could be based on physical differences between the products (Thompson et al., 2018). For example, cheese is a relatively hard and dry product compared to yoghurt and milk, which may affect consumer choice since moister products may be associated with a faster decay (Thompson et al., 2018). On the other hand, consumers' previous experience of how edible they have found these products after the best-before-date could also be driving these observations (Thompson et al., 2018).

4.1 | Strengths and limitations

This study has several strengths and limitations that are worth considering. The relatively large sample size obtained in this study is regarded as a strength since a large sample size is essential for producing reliable, reproducible, and valid results (Blackford, 2017).

In addition, the snowball sampling method used for this study offers both strengths and limitations. One strength is that the method makes it possible to collect a large sample size while simultaneously being time and cost-effective (Abubakar et al., 2015; Baltar & Brunet, 2012). On the other hand, the method increases the risk of selection bias, which can affect the representativeness of the sample (Baltar & Brunet, 2012). This can, for instance, be seen when looking at the relatively high representation of participants with medium and long higher education (Table 2). This lack of representativeness may be because the survey was primarily shared through the authors' networks and, therefore, to some extent, reflects these. In addition, when looking at the distribution for gender (Table 2), an overrepresentation of females was observed. This does not represent the general Danish population since the distribution between males and females is almost equal in Denmark (Statistics Denmark, 2022). Nonetheless, unequal gender distribution is often observed in survey studies, as females are more likely to answer questionnaires compared to males (Smith, 2008).

The participants were also asked about which dairy product category they would buy close to the best-before-date. However, the participants could only choose one product category even though they might purchase several of them. Therefore, the question should have been phrased as "Which of the following dairy product categories do you mostly buy close to the best-before-date?". However, due to the forced choice in the survey, it can be assumed that the participants chose the category they bought most often.

Lastly, the coding scheme chosen for responses to the question regarding the participants' WTB dairy products close to the best-before-date (Table 1) presents several limitations. This is primarily attributed to the two no-opinion response options ("Don't know" and "Do not care about the best-before-date"). Studies have shown that the inclusion of no-opinion responses may undermine the validity of a survey due to difficulties associated with data management (Denman et al., 2018; Krosnick et al., 2002). For this study, it was chosen to assign the response "Don't know" to the value 1 and the response

“Do not care about the best-before-date” to the value 2, while the response “5 days before the best-before-date” was assigned to the value 3. This approach could pose a problem in relation to the segmentation since it may be interpreted as if the participants choosing these no-opinion options will only buy dairy products 6 days or more before the best-before-date. However, this is not necessarily, what the participants may have meant when choosing these response options. For example, the response “Do not care about the best-before-date” may also mean that the participants would like to buy dairy products on the best-before-date. This challenges the validity of the segmentation, as certain participants may have been assigned to a segment to which they did not belong. According to the literature, the most common approach for treating no-opinion responses is to exclude these from the data analysis (Denman et al., 2018). However, this approach would have resulted in a large amount of missing data, since a total of 111 participants would have been excluded from this study. Other methods are to code no-opinion responses as neutral midpoints or treat them as meaningful categorical responses (Denman et al., 2018). However, since the response options for the WTB question were a mix of both categorical (“Don’t know” and “Do not care about the best-before-date”) and interval values (“5 days before the best-before-date,” “4 days before the best-before-date,” etc.), these latter methods were not appropriate for this study. Studies suggest that several factors may cause participants to provide a no-opinion response, such as fear of providing an inaccurate answer or lack of motivation to process the question cognitively and formulate a meaningful response (Denman et al., 2018; Krosnick et al., 2002). Therefore, a possible solution for this study could have been to not provide the participants with no-opinion response options. This thus pushes the participants to do the necessary cognitive work to search their memories for relevant information and integrate this information into a judgment (Krosnick et al., 2002).

5 | CONCLUSION

In this study, the consumers were divided into four segments (Low/Low, Medium/Low, Medium/High, and High/High) according to their frequency of purchasing dairy products close to the best-before-date and their WTB dairy products close to the best-before-date. All four segments had a relatively high understanding of the best-before-date label, and no significant difference in the knowledge score was found between them. Consumers from the Low/Low and Medium/Low segments were, despite their high level of knowledge, less willing to buy dairy products close to the best-before-date compared to the Medium/High and High/High segments. For the Medium/High and High/High segments, drivers for buying dairy products close to the best-before-date were identified as avoidance of food waste, reduced price, and if the products were organic. On the other hand, consumers belonging to the Low/Low and Medium/Low segments refrained from purchasing dairy products close to the best-before-date due to higher risk perception in the form of health concerns and low-quality perception. Furthermore, the consumers belonging to the Low/Low and Medium/Low segments found dairy products close to the best-before-

date unappetizing, which seems to be related to a higher level of food disgust sensitivity. Therefore, the results from this study suggest that consumers' level of risk perception and food disgust sensitivity are the actual drivers or barriers for consumers' WTB dairy products close to the best-before-date and not their level of knowledge concerning the best-before-date label. More specifically, there seems to be a tendency for an age-dependent pattern. This pattern is explained by several factors. One is the higher food disgust sensitivity and high-risk perception of the older respondent, which dominates the Low/Low and Medium/Low segments. Another is the higher attitude toward sustainable behavior driven by environmental concern, food avoidance, and organic product preference for the younger respondents, dominating the High/High segment. These insights could be relevant for retail stores since knowledge about what drives consumers to make purchasing decisions can be used when creating strategies for reducing food waste. More importantly, this study indicates age-related differences in attitudes toward WTB close to the best-before-date products, which may be due to different knowledge and awareness about, for example, the consequences of wasting edible foods that are safe to consume. Further research into the influence of knowledge on attitude and behavior may be analyzed through the use of nudge types presentation, and information could be designed by integrating multiple Sustainable Development Goals to influence consumers' decision-making on buying products close to best-before-date.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Conceptualization: Majken F. Hansen, Michelle Hvidtfeldt, Marlene Lassen, Carina V. Melgaard, Emily Voss, Sujita Pandey, and Marianne Thomsen. Data curation: Majken F. Hansen, Michelle Hvidtfeldt, Marlene Lassen, Carina V. Melgaard, and Emily Voss. Formal analysis: Majken F. Hansen, Michelle Hvidtfeldt, Marlene Lassen, Carina V. Melgaard, Emily Voss and Morten Arendt Rasmussen. Methodology: Majken F. Hansen, Michelle Hvidtfeldt, Marlene Lassen, Carina V. Melgaard, Emily Voss, and Morten Arendt Rasmussen. Resources: Marianne Thomsen. Software: Majken F. Hansen, Michelle Hvidtfeldt, Marlene Lassen, Carina V. Melgaard, Emily Voss, and Morten Arendt Rasmussen. Supervision: Sujita Pandey, Morten Arendt Rasmussen, and Marianne Thomsen. Validation: Sujita Pandey and Marianne Thomsen. Writing—original draft: Majken F. Hansen, Michelle Hvidtfeldt, Marlene Lassen, Carina V. Melgaard, and Emily Voss. Writing—review and editing: Sujita Pandey and Marianne Thomsen. Acquisition: Marianne Thomsen. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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